

Predicting the thermal energy storage and energy discharge of thermal protective clothing

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Introduction

It has long been firmly believed that thermal protective clothing can provide reliable thermal protection against heat and flames. However, the reliability of protective clothing is challenged by the discharge of stored energy [1]. When exposed to heat, protective clothing not only serves as a barrier to protect human skin from hazardous environments, but also stores large amounts of thermal energy depending on the thermal intensity and the property of the fabric [2]. Clothing with energy storage then becomes a passive heating source after exposure and poses thermal hazards to the skin. Therefore, thermal protective clothing may have a dual effect on human skin in reality.

The investigation of energy storage and energy discharge in thermal protective clothing is very important in terms of the understanding of the dual effect of protective clothing. Up until now, it is not firmly known the fabric system contains how much energy storage and how this energy storage contributes to the energy discharge absorbed by the skin. This study focuses on determining the energy storage and energy discharge of thermal protective clothing. Empirical models were established to predict the amounts of energy storage and energy discharge.

Methods

Materials

Fifteen different fabric systems were constructed by commonly used materials in the thermal protective clothing field. The fabric systems were constructed as single-layer fabric, two-layer and multilayer composite systems. The descriptions of materials was shown in a previous study [2,3].

Test apparatus and protocol

A stored energy tester/SET (MTN-P292-08, Measurement Technology Northwest, USA) was employed in this study. A black ceramic thermal flux source was adjusted to deliver a radiative heat flux of 8.5 kW/m². The sensor could be in contact with the fabric system or a spacer could introduce an air gap between the clothing and the sensor. The nominal air gap was 6.4 mm. A set of type-K thermocouples was chosen to measure the temperature distribution through the fabric system. After the preparation of the fabric system with thermocouples, the sample was exposed to the heating source for 600 s. At the end of exposure, the energy storage was discharged either naturally or by means of compression. The test protocol for the forced heat discharge process is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Testing sequence for a multilayer fabric system with an air gap for the forced heat discharge

Calculation of energy storage and energy discharge

The sensible energy storage of a medium is expressed as:

$$Q_{st}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i c_i L_i \frac{\Delta T_{1i}(t) + \Delta T_{2i}(t)}{2} \quad (1)$$

where L refers to the fabric layer thickness in m. $\Delta T_{1i}(t)$ and $\Delta T_{2i}(t)$ are the temperature fluctuations in duration of t on inner and outer surfaces of a fabric layer in K, respectively.

The accumulated energy discharge is calculated as:

$$Q_{rls} = \sum_{t_{exp}}^{t_{exp}+t_{co}} q_{sens}(t) \cdot \Delta t \quad (t \geq t_{exp}) \quad (2)$$

where $q_{sens}(t)$ refers to sensor heat flux at time t in kW/m². t_{exp} and t_{co} refer to exposure time and cooling time of the fabric, respectively.

Results and discussion

Energy storage

It is shown that the energy storage during exposure is increased by the air gap. To further explore the effect of fabric properties and air gap on energy storage (Q_{st}), regression analysis was conducted. The regression equation (3) was significant at level of 0.05 ($p = 0.00$) with the $R^2 = 0.992$.

$$Q_{st} = 0.277 \times W + 3.724 \times AG - 13.022 \quad (3)$$

where W is the weight of the fabric system, and AG is air gap size.

Energy discharge

After the exposure, the energy discharge decreases dramatically with the introduction of an air gap, but significantly increases with the application of the compression. For the natural heat discharge, the air gap reduces heat discharge from the fabric to the skin. However, for the forced heat discharge, the air gap is damaged by the compression. Our previous study has shown that except for the air gap, the innermost fabric layer that is close to the skin also plays a key role in heat discharge [3]. Regression analyses were conducted to examine the heat discharge here. The regression equations (4) and (5) were significant at level of 0.05 ($p = 0.00$) with the $R^2 = 0.919, 0.965$ respectively.

$$\text{Natural energy discharge condition: } Q_{rls-natural} = 0.359 \times Q_{st} - 1.982 \times AG - 5.539 T_{inner} + 26.581 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Forced energy discharge condition: } Q_{rls-forced} = 0.592 \times Q_{st} - 11.057 \times T_{inner} + 14.464 \quad (5)$$

where T_{inner} is the thickness of the innermost fabric layer.

Conclusions

This study investigated the energy storage and energy discharge of thermal protective clothing. The correlation analysis shows that the energy storage during exposure presents a linear relationship with fabric weight and air gap size. The natural energy discharge is linearly related to the energy storage, air gap size and the thickness of the innermost fabric layer, while the forced energy discharge is linearly related to the energy storage and the thickness of the innermost fabric layer.

References

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